

A FOCUS ON THE CONTEXTUALIZED LEARNING ACTIVITY SHEETS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the factors that may affect in constructing the contextualized learning activity sheets based on the learners' results and the teachers' self-assessment using a descriptive correlation research design. The study's findings revealed that the teachers have varied levels of competence in terms of cultural knowledge; on average, they were at the Proficient level of competency. In addition, teachers' self-assessments indicated that they strongly practiced the criteria in constructing contextualized IPED LAS. However, still at the Advanced Beginner level based on the learners' results. It can be concluded that teachers are competent in handling IPED based on their profile and cultural knowledge, yet Advance Beginners in assessment skills. Teachers with higher educational qualifications improved their assessment skills. It is recommended that the regional and division IPED specialist should conduct quarterly training for teachers on the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices (IKSP) and other IPED-related topics. Teachers may conduct indigenization mapping as part of the pedagogical strategy of handling IPED to encourage localization and indigenization of content. With the findings and results, the project ETASIP is made to aid teachers in planning for their assessment strategies.

Keywords: *Assessment Skills, Contextualization, Learning Activity Sheets, Cultural Knowledge, Project ETASIP*

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of contextualization falls on the idea that students learn best when experiences in the classroom have meaning and relevance in their lives. Applying the rule of learning by doing, applied learning, and manipulative learning is also a must in executing localization and contextualization in teaching. The most common way of making learning realistic is through the contextualization of assessments such as learning activity sheets. The main purpose is to improve student learning and motivation to learn. Since a substantial proportion of classroom time is devoted to the assessment for and of student learning, suboptimal assessment practices might hinder desirable student learning and motivation. As such, it seems reasonable to argue that careful consideration of the teachers' classroom assessment and contextualization skills is certainly warranted (Gronlund, et al. 2006).

The current concern in several countries enlightens discussions on the importance of refinement of national cultures as an overall purpose of the curriculum and how this match the idea of contextualizing the learning strategies and activities to suit the needs of students. In America, the issue of weak academic performance has serious implications for the workforce. There is a widening chasm

between the literacy and numeracy skills needed to effectively compete in both the global and national economy and the numbers of students who have mastered these skills, with minority students showing weaker performance than traditional students. With this, American teachers in areas with minorities are required to undergo training to become competent in dealing and assessing with these groups of students with unique needs in education (Baker, et al., 2009).

In the Philippines, both in the cities and remote or rural areas, some of the teachers lack technical know-how in dealing with learners with diverse backgrounds and cultures. This could be one of the reasons why many general education teachers in the country doubted their capacity to teach in an inclusive school. In addition, some in-service teachers said they are willing to handle and work with professionals to include LSEN (Learners with Special Educational Needs) and IPEd (Indigenous Peoples Education) in general education classrooms. However, their overall response based on their knowledge and experience, indicated they are not equipped of handling students with different educational and cultural needs. This problem is further aggravated by the difficulty of incorporating assessment strategies considering that they lacked training and cultural knowledge as non-IP teachers. At this point, teachers, whether trained or otherwise, will have to accept that they will be spread too thin in an inclusionary setting because of the presence of students with special educational and cultural needs in an oversized group of students. The new inclusive education policy requires the preparation of more than one contextualized lesson plan and learning activity sheet. While it has been already adopted in the Philippine Educational System, many school teachers have yet to fully appreciate the value of inclusive education.

In Leyte Division, there are only three IPEd-implementing schools. The IPEd of Leyte Division requires these schools to submit contextualized and indigenized learning lesson plans and learning activities every year. Teachers developed many learning activities for the learners. However, the Division IPEd Education Program Specialist can only conduct validation and observation of teachers once or twice a year. Tooling up contextualization of activities required meticulous planning. Workshops and seminars are insufficient and would not enable IPEd teachers of Dolho Elementary School to meet the standards of high-level assessment skills and contextualization.

It is with these premises, the researcher, being an IPEd teacher, come up with this study with the aim to evaluate the teachers' competence in terms of their assessment skills and cultural knowledge. In addition, this study also targets to determine the factors that may affect constructing the contextualized learning activity sheets based on the learners' test results and teachers' self-assessment results. The latter findings may come up with a proposed output to produce more realistic contextualized learning activities to improve learners' academic performance.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of competence of the teachers in constructing contextualized IPEd learning activity sheets in terms of cultural knowledge?
2. What is the level of competence of the teachers in terms of assessment skills?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' self-assessment and learners' test results?
4. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' profile and their competence in constructing IPEd learning activity sheets?
5. What are the factors that affect the construction of contextualized IPEd learning activity sheets?
6. What output can be proposed out of the findings of the study?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

On Contextualization and Its Legal Basis

Contextualization has been a great part of the Department of Education as mandated in the 1987 Philippine Constitution. It is clearly stated under Sec. 10.2, Implementing Rules and Regulations for RA 10533 which says that The curriculum shall be contextualized and global and the curriculum shall be flexible enough to enable and allow schools to localize, indigenize, and enhance [the curriculum] based on their respective educational and social contexts. It is also clearly stated in Article XIV, Section 14 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution which states that The State shall foster the preservation, enrichment, and dynamic evolution of a Filipino national culture based on the principle of unity in diversity in a climate of free artistic and intellectual expression. The DepEd Mission has also emphasized the importance of contextualization and localization in the preservation of the culture of one's place which says To protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education.

Learning is a function not only of the activity itself but also of the context and the culture in which it takes place (Gillespie, 2002). That is why there is Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL), also known as Contextualized Instruction. It is defined as a diverse family of instructional strategies designed to more seamlessly link the learning of foundational skills and academic or occupational content by focusing teaching and learning squarely on concrete applications in a specific context that is of interest to the student (Mazzeo et al., 2008). In other words, CTL is a process built on the recognition that some students learn more effectively when they are taught in a hands-on, real-world context rather than in an abstract manner. Effective learning (EL) requires not only the acquisition but the active application of knowledge, skills, and processes (Gillespie, 2002).

Everyone has experienced how learning an appropriate name for what was dim and vague cleared up and crystallized the whole matter. Some meaning seems distinct almost within reach, but is elusive; it refuses to condense into definite form; the attaching of a word somehow puts limits around the meaning, draws it out from the void, and makes it stand out as an entity on its own account.

Through the contextualized curriculum, the context is intended to provide additional cognitive and affective information to the learner beyond the targeted content knowledge (Giamellaro, 2014). This intention is manifested when the process of contextualizing knowledge occurs through experience (Roth & Jornet, 2013). Realized contextualization, then, is a process of learning as situated in a setting in which the social and material environment can contribute meaningfully to the development of knowledge. As a process, knowledge is given meaning through connections between the learner's conceptual understanding of an idea and the environment in which it was learned, recalled, used, or collectively situated (Giamellaro et al., 2014). Ideally, an educator could contextualize the curriculum, and support the learner to contextualize her learning which results in contextualized knowledge in a function that could be modeled. Contextualized knowledge, as process and outcome, could also be described as explicitly situated such that the learner can recognize the connections between the content and context, albeit with varying qualities of articulation. If this content-context connection is explicitly recognizable then it can also be conceptualized as an outcome measure of educational experiences and serve as an indicator of the degree to which the experience explicitly situated the knowledge for the learner.

Another focus for curricular contextualization development is pedagogical practice, that is, teachers' approaches within the classroom context, and how they contribute to increasing students' outcomes as learning promoters (Bustos-Orosa et al., 2008). To achieve curricular contextualization, one must employ diverse pedagogical practices to be able to promote learning and to establish classroom environments and dynamics, adequate to students' distinct needs, expectations, interests, rhythms, and styles (Leite & Fernandes et al., 2010). Teachers are responsible for creating a well-functioning environment and establishing an equilibrium between the national curriculum and a contextualized curriculum. Nevertheless, as emphasized, this can be a tricky process that presents some difficulties for teachers, especially when it requires new approaches and methods (Choppin & Davies, 2009).

Therefore, the way teachers act, the way they plan and execute their class programs, how they manage the classroom, and how they set up the teaching and learning environment are the key aspects of student's success and are central when defining and conceiving curricular contextualization (Doyle et al., 2009).

Emphasizing the place, one can build a curriculum that is close to students' lived and experienced reality, in which subject content can easily be related to real-life situations, increasing students' understanding of such matters (Imand Pak, et al., 2012). A researcher presented a perspective

on place-based education and states, "Teaching in this way does not require the elimination of non-local knowledge so much as the simple inclusion of the local." It is possible to relate this with curricular contextualization given that it stands for the use of knowledge already close to students to reach for the abstract knowledge of school subjects, increasing understanding and learning. This is presented as place-based education, basing the teaching and learning process on the local and extending it to the global (Smith, 2005). This perspective is shared by another researcher who considers that "The subject matter and learning processes in the curriculum should also be relevant to the daily lives of the people." They should be based on the knowledge that comes from the local environment and economic surroundings. They should deal with the people's problems and the needs of the local communities, which arise in a different manner in each environment (Sahasewiyon, 2004).

In summary, teachers should be adaptive and creative in using localization and contextualization in teaching. Such principles were made and adapted in the academe to make the curriculum responsive, and flexible to the needs of the learners, especially 21st-century learners. These learners need to be holistically and skillfully developed. Yes, it is true that sometimes we understand more the concepts by relating them to ideas that can easily comprehend, appreciate, and relate to in our lives, but the standards of quality and relevant education should always be considered all the times and should not be compromised just for the sake of localized and contextualized lesson.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed descriptive correlation design by Lathom-Radocy and Radocy (1995) which intends to determine the relationship between two or more variables and gives an indication of how one variable may affect the other. It is employed in this study to evaluate the relationship of the teacher's competence in the construction of contextualized IPEd Learning Activity Sheet.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 22 IPEd teachers of Dolho Elementary School purposively selected. The researcher selected 20 learners per grade level who were chosen using simple random sampling for both IP and non-IP learners.

The study was carried out at Dolho Elementary School, an IPEd-implementing school located in Barangay Dolho, Bato, Leyte, where the researcher is assigned. This is 4 km away from its municipality and it is led by a school principal, and 23 classroom teachers.

Research Instrument

The researcher adopted a 20-item researcher-made test for the teacher to evaluate their cultural knowledge which was validated by the IP consultant. Another three sets of teacher-made contextualized test learning activity sheets with a table of the specifications were also used to determine the assessment skills of the teachers. Items were taken from the second quarter of the school year 2020-2021. A 10-item test was given to Kindergarten until Grade 3 learners and a 15-item test was administered to the Grade 4 – Grade 6 learners. All tests administered were multiple choice type of tests. A 10-item Self – assessment checklist was also given to teachers as part of the self-evaluation of their assessment skills in constructing multiple-choice tests.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to treat the gathered data in order to answer queries of the study:

MPS was used in determining the level of competence of the teachers in constructing the learning activity sheets

Weighted Mean was used to determine the teacher's competence in terms of self-assessment and learners' test results.

Eta Coefficient Test Statistics was used to evaluate the strength of association between the teachers' profile and their competence in constructing IPEd LAS.

Cronbach Alpha was used to assess the reliability or internal consistency of a set of scale or test items for the cultural knowledge and assessment skill questionnaires.

Pearson's r Correlation was used between the teaching and educational profile of the teachers and the level of competence of Dolho Elementary School teachers in constructing IPEd learning activity sheets.

t-test was applied to test the significance of the relationship between learners' level of competence of the teachers in constructing the contextualized learning activity sheets and the academic performance of the learners.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The Teachers' Profile

The teachers were profiled based on their educational qualifications, number of hours of relevant training, and teaching experience using the questionnaire designed for the purpose. Tables 1, 2, and 3 show the profile of the teachers.

Table 1. Teachers' Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	Number of Cases	Percentage
College Graduate	1	4.5
Masteral with Units	19	86.4
MA Graduate	2	9.1
Doctoral with Units	0	0
Doctorate Degree	0	0
Others	0	0
Total	22	100

Most of the teachers have already started their Master's Education and only two of them are MA graduates. There is a high percentage of teachers who already earned master's units since the school administrators encouraged teachers to grow professionally through post-graduate education. This is true in the works of Harris & Sass (2011) which emphasized the relevance of a Master's education in raising the teacher's status in the teaching profession. Likewise, in the study of Hill (2007), it was found that teachers are frequently encouraged to pursue postgraduate units as a vital part of their professional growth and development.

This outcome implies that teachers are now giving importance and emphasis to their educational qualifications. They consider higher educational qualifications as an important factor to improve their competencies.

The succeeding table shows the data on teachers' number of hours of relevant training.

Table 2. Teachers Number of Hours of Relevant Training

Number of Hours of Training	Number of Cases	Percentage	Mean Hours of Training	Standard Deviation
0	8	36.36		
1 – 24	6	27.27		
25 – 48	2	9.09		
49 – 72	3	13.64	47.27	86.27
73 – 96	1	4.55		
More than 96	2	9.09		
Total	22	100.00		

As reflected in the number of cases, about one-third of the teachers had never undergone relevant training, mostly are newly assigned teachers. However, a good number of them have attended the utmost 24 hours of training. A few have done 48 hours, 72 hours, 96 hours, and more than 96 hours of training. The IPEd coordinator of the school acquired the greatest number of trainings with 300 hours in total. As reflected in the average weighted mean, the teachers have attended around 47.27 hours of relevant training with a very large standard deviation of 86.27, indicative of a wide disparity between the training experiences of the teachers. This is supported in the study of Zhang and Burry-Stock (2003) which emphasized that the number of teachers involved in training goes higher from the past years to the present due to its importance in professional development.

The results denote that majority of the faculty have undergone training on IPED Instruction yet insufficient which may cause teachers to be incompetent in handling classes for the Badjaos. This may indicate that teachers may need more relevant training and experiences for them to be more competent and to lessen the challenges they may have in relation to the matter.

Furthermore, table 3 reveals the data on teachers' years of experience as IPED Teachers.

Table 3. Teachers' Years of Experience as IPED Teacher

Number of Years	Number of Cases	Percentage
0 -2	2	9.1
3- 5	7	31.8
6 – 7	3	13.6
8 – 10	4	18.2
11 – 12	2	9.1
13 and above	4	18.2
Total	22	100

The result shows that teachers teaching IPED had a variety of years of teaching experience. A high percentage is reflected in 3-5 years since there is a high number of new teachers in the school with 5 years of experience below. This is followed by 8-10 and more than 13 years of experience. The rest of the teachers were almost evenly divided for the other ranges of teaching experience. The data gathered is similar to the study results of Alsarimi and Mertler (1999) which highlighted the importance of teaching experience in their teaching practice and mastery of assessment strategies.

This result suggests that the majority of the teachers are experienced IPED teachers, and their years of service are indicative of their competence in handling IPED instruction. It also implies that experience can enhance teaching competence.

The Teachers' Level of Competence in Terms of Cultural Knowledge

The teachers' level of competence was measured based on their cultural knowledge using a questionnaire that consisted of 20 items, constructed, and validated by an expert. Tables 4, 5, and 6 summarized the results.

Table 4. Competency Level of the Teachers' Cultural Knowledge

Competency Level	Number of Cases	Percentage	Mean Percentage Score	Standard Deviation	Overall Competence Level
Expert	6	27.27			
Proficient	1	4.55			
Competent	8	36.36	71.82	14.02	Proficient
Advanced	3	13.64			
Beginner	4	18.18			
Novice					

Overall	22	100.00
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Legend: Master (84-100), Expert (76-83), Proficient (68-75), Advance Beginner (60-67), Novice (below 60)

The teachers are in a wide array of competencies in terms of cultural knowledge as reflected by the standard deviation implying a wide variation of teachers' competency in terms of cultural knowledge. More than a third of them can be classified as **Competent**. More than a quarter can be considered **Expert**, followed by **novices** and the rest were either **Advanced beginners** or **Proficient**. On average, the teachers are considered to be **Proficient** at an MPS of 71.82. The outcome is in consonance with the results of the study by Zhang & Burry-Stock (2003) which stipulates that teachers are responsible for evaluating their own assessment ways, instructions, and student learning, teachers need to develop assessment skills. Liaw, (2006) also proved that teachers must explore the learners' culture through discussion of the value system, expectations, traditions, customs, and rituals they unconsciously take part in before they are able to reflect upon other cultures with a "higher degree of intellectual objectivity".

From the result, it can be inferred that teachers are culturally aware of the cultural traditions and practices of Badjaos. In addition, their interaction with their Badjao learners has enhanced their knowledge of the culture of the indigenous people under their care as loco parentis.

The Teachers' Competence in Terms of Assessment Skills

The teachers were made to answer a self-assessment checklist to gauge their competence in constructing the contextualized IPED LAS. Table 5 shows the summary.

Table 5. Teachers' Self –assessment of Their Assessment Skills

Item Number	Assessment Skills Statement	Average Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Rank
1	I specify the Learning Outcomes on what the test items should measure.	4.86	0.351	Strongly Practiced	2.5
2	I emphasize higher level thinking based on the content of the items.	4.55	0.510	Strongly Practiced	7.5
3	I use language and vocabulary that is appropriate for the group being tested, that even poor readers will understand.	4.86	0.351	Strongly Practiced	2.5
4	I edit and proof all items, prompts and instructions to make sure grammar, punctuation, capitalization, and spelling are correct.	4.95	0.213	Strongly Practiced	1
5	I am conservative in the use of words and pictures to make sure that items do not assume racial, class, and gender stereotypes.	4.64	0.581	Strongly Practiced	9
6	I make sure that minority/ indigenous peoples' interests are considered and are well-presented.	4.82	0.395	Strongly Practiced	4
7	I clearly state each item in the form of a question or an incomplete.	4.59	0.503	Strongly Practiced	6
8	I write 1 correct or best answer and several plausible distractors for the choices.	4.73	0.456	Strongly Practiced	5

9	I eliminate excessive wordings and irrelevant information from the stem.	4.55	0.510	Strongly Practiced	7.5
10	I randomly distribute the correct response and limit the number of alternatives (between 3 – 5 alternatives/ choices per question).	4.50	0.598	Strongly Practiced	10
Overall		4.70	0.196	Strongly Practiced	

Legend: Strongly Practiced (4.20 – 5.00), Moderately Practiced (3.40 – 4.19), Practiced (2.60 – 3.39), Fairly Practiced (1.80 – 2.59), Not Practiced (1.00 – 1.79)

As reflected in the result, it has an average weighted mean of 4.70 for the 10-item self-assessment checklist. This score classifies them at the Strongly Practiced level. This means that they saw themselves to be having excellent practice in making their assessment tests. The small standard deviation of 0.196 would have implied that they have a very closed perception of their assessment skills with the other teachers. The teachers scored themselves at the Strongly Practiced level for all the items in the self-assessment checklist. Top of the list is item 4, *I edit and proof all items prompts, and instructions to make sure grammar, punctuation, capitalization, and spelling are correct*, then followed by item 1, *I specify the Learning Outcomes on what the test items should measure*, and item 3, *I use language and vocabulary that is appropriate for the group being tested, that even poor readers will understand*. Last on the ranking is item 10, *I randomly distribute the correct response and limit the number of alternatives (between 3 – 5 alternatives/ choices per question)*. The variation of the scoring ranges from low to moderate as manifested by the standard deviations for each item.

In the research of Ohlsen (2007), classroom assessments serve many important purposes, and most teachers are confident that they are skilled in dealing with assessments on the identification of students with special learning needs, motivation of students, clarification of student achievement expectations, and monitoring instructional effectiveness. The result is also relative to the study of Zhang and Burry-Stock (2003) which argued that teachers' perceived skill in classroom assessment practices reflects their perceptions of their skill in conducting classroom assessment practices. The result, it shows that teachers are positive that they acquire relevant skills and knowledge in assessment based on their self-monitoring and that they are confident in dealing with assessment activities.

The succeeding table shows the data on teachers' competence in terms of assessment skills based on the learners' results.

Table 6. Teachers' Competence in Terms of Assessment Skills Based on Learners' Test Results

Competency Level	Number of Cases	Percentage	Mean Percentage Score	Standard Deviation	Overall Competence Level
Expert	0	0.00			
Proficient	1	4.55			
Competent	5	22.73			
Advanced Beginner	7	31.82	61.20	9.02	Advanced Beginner
Novice	9	40.91			
Overall	22	100.00			

Legend: Master (84 – 100), Expert (76 – 83), Proficient (68 - 75), Advance Beginner (60-67), Novice (below 60)

None of the teachers are considered Expert in terms of their competency in Assessment skills. In fact, many of them are considered *Novices*. Then a good number of them are *Advanced Beginners*, followed by *Competent* and only one is considered *Proficient*. On average, the teachers were classified

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at the *Advanced Beginner* level, where teachers begin to understand what they have been doing in the assessment strategies and were able to obtain more information relative to the teaching-learning. The result also reflects a considerable SD implying a wide variety of assessment skills. This is connected to the study of Ohlsen (2007) clearly emphasized that the learners' ability and learning styles may affect and reflect the teacher's assessment skill, and learners need to be considered.

From the result, it is imperative that teachers need to enhance their assessment skills by attending more relevant training and may pursue graduate studies. Moreover, the teachers may consult or share their best practices with other teachers to improve their assessment skills.

The Relationship between the Assessment Skills of the Teachers Based on Self-Assessment and Student Test Results

The relationship between the self-assessment skills and assessment skills based on the results of the test of the students was correlated. Table 7 shows the results.

Table 7. Coefficient of Correlation between the Assessment Skills of the Teachers

Variables	Pearson, r	Strength of Relationship	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Self-Assessment Students' Test	-.094	Very Weak Negative	.678	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Their correlation coefficient of -.094 indicated a very weak negative correlation. The p-value of .678 was not significant. Thus, it failed to reject the null hypothesis of no significant relationship. There is no relationship between the assessment skills of the teachers as gauged by themselves and measured through the test results of the students. This is contrary to the study of Brown & Harris (2013) which emphasized that self-assessment does contribute positively to learning outcomes, but its effects are highly variable, with many threats to its validity on the student's performance and written results. The study of McMillan (2008) asserted that teachers' beliefs and perceptions that affect their assessment and the results of their practice are not constant.

The result presented above shows that the student's test results cannot define the assessment skills of the teacher and may depend on environmental factors.

The Significant Relationship between Teachers' Profile and Competence

The Eta Coefficient Test Statistic was used to determine the significance of the relationship between the numerical dependent and the categorical independent variable. The independent variables are educational qualifications while the dependent variable was cultural knowledge. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to measure the association between the numerical variables. Tables 8 and 9 show the results.

Table 8. Coefficient of Correlation between Assessment Skills Based on Students Test Results and Educational Qualification and Years of Experience of the Teachers

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Eta Coefficient test statistic (η)	Strength of Correlation	Minimum Level of Acceptance	Decision	Remarks
Educational Qualification	Assessment Skills	0.591	Moderate	0.20	Reject H_0	Significant
Years of Experience		0.510	Moderate	0.20	Reject H_0	Significant

There was a moderate association between the educational qualification and assessment skills of the teachers. This association had a value of η of 0.591 which is greater than 0.20. Thus, the relationship between educational qualification and the assessment skills of the teachers is significant. The study of Harris & Sass (2011) has also proved that graduate education may improve teacher

effectiveness and raise the status of the teaching profession. Collier (2013) found that math assessment scores of students whose teachers had a postgraduate degree were significantly higher than those of students whose teachers did not have a master's or doctoral degree.

The same can be observed with the association between the number of years of experience and the assessment skills of the teachers. There was a moderate association for an η of 0.510 which was greater than 0.20. The association was significant. There was a significant relationship between the years of experience and the assessment skills of the teachers. Similar to the result of the studies of (Rice 2003) and Rockoff (2004) which found that years of a teacher's career, accruing more years of experience seems to be more strongly related to student achievement., when comparing teacher effectiveness to student test scores in the assessment of reading and mathematics.

The results above suggest that educational background and years of experience are important factors to become effective assessors of learning. More exposure to these indigenous learners and postgraduate units/degrees leads to the development of the teacher's skills in assessment.

The succeeding table presents the data on the correlation between the training experience and assessment skills of the teacher.

Table 9. Coefficient of Correlation between Training Experience and Assessment Skills of the Teachers

Variables	Pearson, r	Strength of Relationship	p – value	Decision	Remarks
Training Experience Assessment Skills Based on Student's Test	0.225	Weak Positive	.313	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Assessment skills based on students' test and training experience also had a weak positive linear correlation for an r-value of 0.225. It failed to reject the null hypothesis of no significant relationship. There is no relationship between the training experience and assessment skills of the teacher. Self-assessment skills had a very weak correlation with training. The relationship is not significant; hence the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is not rejected. Training does not influence the assessment skills of the teachers. This is contradicted by the study of Miller (2015) which emphasized that training teachers from the school can help in bridging the gap between theory and practice and can enhance teachers' professional development in terms of classroom management and assessment.

The results above suggest that training experience is not the sole factor that can help enhance the assessment skills and cultural knowledge of the teachers. The number of days of training is not a basis of a teacher's competence, but rather, it is the teacher's application of the learnings gained even in a short period of such training.

Factors Affecting the Construction of Contextualized IPED LAS.

An open-ended question was answered by 23 respondents. This is to identify the other possible factors that could affect the construction of contextualized IPED LAS. The respondents were asked to answer the following questions based on their opinion to have a view of the factors that are experienced by the IPED teachers on the construction of contextualized IPED LAS.

To show the common responses of the teachers, table 10 is presented below.

Table 10. Identified Factors Affecting the Construction of Contextualized IPED LAS

Factors	Description	Sample Verbatim
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices 	Teachers' cultural awareness and background of a particular indigenous group.	<i>Most of the teachers said that Indigenous knowledge is important to connect the content with their culture as part of contextualization.</i>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content Knowledge of the teacher 	<p>Teacher's mastery of the content across all relevant subjects.</p>	<p><i>Most of the teachers said that the content knowledge of the teacher reflects the way how the LAS is created whether it gives with the content or not.</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant IPED Training and Workshops 	<p>Teachers' professional growth and development in terms of the program through training and workshops.</p>	<p><i>Most of the teachers said that IPED training and workshops can help teachers enhance their pedagogical methods in constructing IPED LAS and lesson plans</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of IPED books, guides, and other references 	<p>The relevant sources of information needed in the construction of contextualized IPED LAS</p>	<p><i>Most of them complained that it is difficult for them to contextualize since they are not native speakers of the IP dialect. Thus, there is a need for resources to effectively construct the IPED LAS.</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment Skills and Competence 	<p>Teachers' ability to make and use effective assessment methods based on the learner's needs and capacity.</p>	<p><i>Most of the teachers said that in order to construct a valid and reliable contextualized LAS, one should be competent in the different assessment methods and strategies considering the IP and non-IP learners.</i></p>

The result of the study revealed that there are five major factors affecting the construction of the contextualized IPED LAS which are: indigenous knowledge systems and practices, content knowledge of the teacher, relevant IPED training and workshops, presence of IPED books, guides, and other references, and assessment skills and competence. These answers were gathered through an interview with the teachers.

The **Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices** include how the teachers connect with the learner's understanding of the content and assessment to the local and traditional knowledge that is present in the community. Teachers with cultural knowledge find it easy to construct contextualized learning activity sheets than those who have none. It implies that teachers' indigenous knowledge can affect how the teacher constructs the contextualized IPED LAS. The study by Howard & Clarence (2011) stipulated that "culturally responsive pedagogy" is an intervention method of teaching in attaining the IP and non-IP learners' outcomes of what they have understood from the discussions and evaluation of their teachers. **Content knowledge of the teacher** affects how the teachers interpret the content goals they are expected to reach with their students. It affects the way we hear and respond to our students and their questions. It affects our ability to explain clearly and to ask good questions especially since contextualization adds a challenge in the construction of the LAS. It is supported by the study of Ball (2000) which highlighted that teachers need a sufficient conceptual framework into which they can incorporate insights and sufficient support and opportunities for reflection in order to make use of the potential for content learning embedded in their teaching practices.

It is the goal of the Department of Education that every teacher will become not only efficient but also effective in terms of teaching and assessment, especially in special programs like IPED. Therefore, **relevant IPED training and workshops** can affect teachers on how they cater to new methods and techniques in teaching. These also include orientations on the background of the IPED program and training on how to become efficient in constructing IPED LAS as one of the vital elements in the child's learning. The findings of the study of Acquah (2016) supported and showed teachers' awareness of the importance of acknowledging cultural diversity in the school and its relevance in connecting to school life, which is an important step in breaking homogenized visions on the school community and students' identities, and developing culturally relevant pedagogies. What is required now is reliable and valid information about the effectiveness and the actual learning outcomes of the newly developed materials.

The **presence of IPED books, guides, and other references** can contribute to the content and the construction of IPED LAS since the teachers are not native Sinama speakers. It can truly affect how they connect national competency to indigenized knowledge. Assessment is a critical step in the learning process. **Assessment skills and competence** allow teachers to see if their teaching has been effective. The assessment also allows teachers to ensure that students learn what they need to know in order to meet the course's learning objectives. The effectiveness measurement of teacher assessment skills is clearly emphasized in the study of Darling & Hammond (2010) as important as the development of the teacher itself. Therefore, the perception of the teacher should not be focused only on the learning achievement of learners, but also on mastering the competence of teachers. Assessment competence of the teachers affects many facets of education, including student grades, placement, and advancement as well as curriculum, instructional needs, and catering special programs like IPED.

CONCLUSION

Teachers' competence improved with better educational qualifications. Cultural knowledge and assessment skills are honed with better education, training, and experience. However, other factors of learners' learning could be limited by contextualization and indigenization.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are summarized: School administrators may include attendance to relevant training for teachers teaching IPED as part of their professional development. The School system may encourage teachers to finish their graduate studies. The School system may establish a program to encourage teachers to continue teaching in the IPED program. The teachers may conduct indigenization mapping as part of the pedagogical strategy of handling IPED to encourage localization and indigenization of content. Regional and Division IPED specialists may conduct quarterly training and seminars for teachers on the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices (IKSP) and other IPED-related topics. Future researchers may conduct related studies on the following: a. The effect of teachers' cultural and assessment skills on the academic performance of the learners in the IPED program. b. The relationship of the teachers' profile to the academic performance of the learners in The IPED program.

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